

STATE VS INDIGENOUS PEOPLE: CONFLICT ON FOREST RESOURCES AT BUKIT DUABELAS NATIONAL PARK (TNBD)

M. Yusuf¹, Syafrial¹

¹ STISIP NH Jambi
syafri2009@gmail.com

Abstract

Determination of Bukit Duabelas area into TNBD in Jambi Province has raised conflict between management of TNBD with indigenous people called Orang Rimba who have been living within the park. Basically, the establishment of the National Park aims to protect and preserve Orang Rimba's life and culture. Unfortunately, it worries them. The rules made limit the access of Orang Rimba to use any forest resource which they have been utilized it for generations traditionally. BTBND remains the conservation aspect while Orang Rimba keeps their traditional ways based on their costumes in exploiting forest resources. This study uses a case study approach to explore the dynamics of the conflict, the mapping of actors, issues and the context of the conflict, and the causes of the emergence and continuing conflict. This study revealed that the management policy of national park that prematurely born and the exclusion of indigenous people's involvement as part of the conflict for many parties. The ambiguity between conservation and by maintaining the living people in the area has been used by some people to access the forest resources and even for the land ownership in the area.

DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.2549114

1. Introduction

The existence and access toward natural resources have impact on human life, wealth distribution, power structure and group identity, unfortunately they also as the sources of conflict. The conservation is intended to protect and manage the natural resources, and also to improve human life are considered as an effective way to minimize the sources of conflict. However, it is not run as what supposed to be. In practice, the conservation created the conflict between local community and government. In other words, the conservation limits the access of local community toward natural resource in which it is as their occupation. Limited access has created economic problem, because the conservation leads to injustice in profit distribution (Hammill, Craig, Malpas, & Matthew, 2009).

The determination on conservation area intended to protect various plants and animals from inexistence and to maintain ecosystem. Unfortunately, in the implementation, protection aspect plays more rather on the usage of the natural resources aspect (Prabowo, Basuni, & Suharjito, 2010). Because of that, the conservation area which is in form of national park and managed centrally, since the beginning of its establishment has faced various problems. But unfortunately the solving solution tended to use legal approach, so that another conflict raised after the previous conflict solved (Sembiring, Basuni, & Soekmadi, 2010).

The problems occurred at Bukit Duabelas National Park (Taman Nasional Bukit Duabelas/TNBD), Jambi Province. The park with 60.500 hectare located at three areas; Batanghari for + 65% or 37.000 hectare, Sarolangun for + 15% or around 9.000 hectare; and Tebo for around 20% or 11.500 hectare (Bakker & Moniaga, 2010; Sylviani, 2008). At the beginning, the aims of making this kind of National Park was to protect and to conserve the place and culture of "Orang Rimba" as the indigeneus people who have been living there for years. Their life totally depends on the forest. But unfortunately, now their life has been threatened by some conflicts of the forest for various interests. This research explores the dynamic, actor, and causes of conflict in National Park management.

2. Method of the Study

This is an exploratory qualitative research with case study approach. The data gotten from three villages: Sei Ruan Ulu village (Batanghari District), Pematang Kabau village (Sarolangun district), and Tanah Garo village (Tebo District). Two main sources of data used in this research, they are; first, primary data which is gotten from both structured and non-structured interview combined with observation. Snowball ampling was used in determining the respondent which consisted of TNBD officer, Orang rimba, KKI Warsi, Sokola Rimba, and villagers. Second, secondary data was gotten from previous researches. The data gotten was analyzed by using interactive model data analysis; data reduction, data presentation, and making conclusion and verification.

3. Findings and Discussion

Conflicts

Conflict occurred at management of TNBD consists of two parts. First, before Momentum of Understanding, second after Momentum of Understanding between government and stakeholders. In 2004-2008, first conflict happened. The conflict was not only between indigenous people (Orang Rimba) with government, but also involved villagers, company, and the persons who has needs and activities within the area. The conflict keeps continue with various forms and causes. According to Sardi (2010), the conflict ended after the managerial of BKSDA Jambi substituted by Balai TNBD which formatted through Permenhut No. P.29/Menhut-II/2006 on June 2nd, 2006. Since 2007, BTNBD has begun doing his duty. Nevertheless, other new problems rose related with zoning system.

In 2009-2016 happened the conflict after MoU has made. In December 2009, the MoU made as the victory of Orang Rimba. It was supported with SK Menhutbun No.258/kpts-II/2000 stated that TNBD as the place for living and live of Orang Rimba. That statement as the main sources to access the whole things available in the forest. After zoning system has been made, the conflict focused on two main actors. They are BTNBD and Orang Rimba. The MoU made has been inferred as the conflict solution. In the hope that zoning system were able to avoid the problem arose between them, but unfortunately it was procedurally not run well. This was seen from the survey in the field and discussion conducted by different persons from Orang Rimba's representative. According to Suharko (2016), the conflict occurred between BTNBD and Orang Rimba can be divided into two actors; main actor and supporting actor. The main actor who has conflict toward the access of forest resources at national park is between BTNBD and

Orang Rimba. But, in fact, not all Orang Rimba involved directly in the conflict both laten and manifestation. So, mapping the actors of the conflict from orang Rimba is necessary to be done.

Grouping the actors of the conflict based on Orang Rimba'a attitude. If the policy made is benefit for them, so they will support it. On the contrary, if the policy has no benefit at all for them, so they rejected it. This attitude actually made the grouping process faced difficulty in identifying who are pro and contra toward the policy.

Orang Rimba who involved in the conflict are those who generally in transition condition and those who have assimilated with the villagers. On the contrary, Orang Rimba who still stay in the forest and those who still strict on their culture are those who pro to the policy of national park management.

Causes of the Continued Conflict

National Park Bukit Duabelas (TNBD) is the first unique national park in Indonesia, because not only the forest resources in that park become the conservation area, but also the people who live and stay inside the park also legally become part of the conservation. Unfortunately, the conflict for access in the forest become the source of the problem then. The conflict for the forest between the indigenous people with other actors become more complicated because of limited access for the forest to get any benefits from it (Agung, 2011). There are two different points of view of TNBD. First, for indigenous people who has been living inside the forest, hunting and do anything there in order to mantain their life, also they regarded that forest is the gift from their ancestors to live and stay there. (Bakker & Moniaga, 2010; Steinebach & Kunz, 2017). If it is seen from the needs of indigenous people, there are at least three basic needs. First, forest as their home. Second, any forest resource such as wood, fruits, medicine, and animals are sold to get money to fulfill others needs (Novriyanti, Burhanuddin, & Bismark, 2014). Third, as the culture value and custom-built such as the existance of burial plot, birth plot, and Pasoron plot (Takiddin, 2014). Orang Rimba keeps running their cultural habit which is very important to show their identity and legitimation toward their land (Potter, 2008; Rokhdian, 2012).

Second, from point of view of the government, the decision of determining national park area was intended to conserve the forest. Unfortunately, it created dualism policy. In one side, it conserve the forest, at the other side, it also for the living of the people who live and stay in the forest. The conflict occured because of ambiguity and competition between the government's rule and Orang Rimba's costumes. Aside of that, the policy that was made has failed in understanding local context(Orang Rimba's custom and social economy condition), the policy framework of conservation tended not aspirative. The opposition influenced the implementation of the policy because the local community is able to access the forest resource (Kurniadi & Rumboko, 2015).

4. Conclusion

The National Park's management can create coflicts from varies background. The conflict keeps increase anytime. Instrumentalic policy created various responds from stakeholders who directly have interest in it. The government keeps applying the policy in order to implement the national park which based on laws. Moreover, to run the law, at the end it always rise the conflict because

each area has its own characteristics, and the law created by government contradictory with the costumes Orang Rimba. This case become the major causes of the conflicts never stop.

The indigenous people's struggling in order to get their rights to use costum's law, local history and power in any form has proven able to strenghten their position toward the aces of forest resources. By conservating the forest without giving any chances for orang rimba to involve caused multidimention conflicts.

By seeing the conflict's phenomenon happened at TNBD, hopefully there is alternative solution through forest's management based on community is needed to be proposed and applied. Because, orang rimba potentialy are not only as an object, but aslo as the subject of conservation.

References

- [1] Afiff, S., & Lowe, C. (2007). Claiming Indigenous Community: Political Discourse and Natural Resources Right in Indonesia. *Alternatives*, 32, 73–79.
- [2] Agung, P. (2011). Rencana Tata Ruang Wilayah dan Distribusi Manfaat Sumberdaya Hutan. *World Agroforestry Centre*, (12), 1–4.
- [3] Anjarwati, E. (2008). ANjarwati, E. (2008). Mainstreaming Local Wisdom: Indigenous People Collective Action in Rainforest Management (The Case of Indonesia and Philippines). *ainstreaming Local Wisdom: Indigenous People Collective Action in Rainforest Management (The Case of In*.
- [4] Bakker, L., & Moniaga, S. (2010). The Space Between: Land Claims and the Law in Indonesia. *Asian Journal of Social Science*, 38, 187–203. <https://doi.org/10.1163/156853110X490890>
- [5] Cote, D. J., & Cliche, L. (2011). Indigenous Peoples' Resistance to Oil Palm Plantation in Borneo. *Kasarinlan: Philippine Journal of Third World Studies*, 26(1–2), 121–152.
- [6] Darmanto. (2011). Konservasi Global, Taman Nasional dan Praktek Lokal Di Pulau Siberut, Sumatera Barat. *Jurnal Ilmu Kehutanan*, V(1), 52–65.
- [7] Deni. (2011). Analisis Perambahan Hutan Di Taman Nasional Bukit Barisan Selatan (Studi Kasus Desa Tirom Kecamatan Pematang Sawa Kabupaten Tanggamus). *Jurnal Ilmu Kehutanan*, V(1), 9–20.
- [8] Dunggio, I., & Gunawan, H. (2009). NASIONAL DI INDONESIA (An Overview on The History of National Park Management Policy in Indonesia). *Jurnal Analisis Kebijakan Kehutanan*, 6(1), 43–56. Retrieved from <http://ejournal.forda-mof.org/ejournal-litbang/index.php/JAKK/article/view/338>
- [9] Hammill, A., Craig, R., Malpas, R., & Matthew, R. (2009). *Conflict-Sesitive Conservation Practitioners' Manual*. Sustainable Development. Manitoba, Canada.
- [10] Hauser-Schäublin, B. (Ed.). (2013). *Adat and Indigeneity in Indonesia: Culture and Entitlements between Heteronomy and Self-Ascription*, 7, 1–250.
- [11] Hull, S. (2009). The “Everyday Politics” of IDP Protection in Karen State. *Journal of Current Southeast Asian Affairs*, 28(2), 7–21.
- [12] KomnasHAM. (2007). *Laporan Akhir Pemantauan Dugaan Pelanggaran Hak Masyarakat Adat Orang Rimba*.
- [13] Kurniadi, R., & Rumboko, L. (2015). Implementasi Kebijakan Silvopastur di Cagar Alam Gunung Mutis dan Perlawanan Masyarakat Lokal. *Jurnal Ilmu Sosial Dan Ilmu Politik*, 19(2), 169–179.

- [14] Kusworo, A. (2014). Resource Control, Conflict, and Collaboration. In Pursuing Livelihoods, Imagining Development (pp. 93–109). ANU Press.
- [15] Larson, A. M. (2013). Hak Tenurial dan Akses Ke Hutan Manual pelatihan untuk penelitian. Bogor, Indonesia: CIFOR.
- [16] Novriyanti, Burhanuddin, M., & Bismark, M. (2014). Pola dan Nilai Lokal Etnis Dalam Pemanfaatan Satwa Pada Orang Rimba Bukit Duabelas Provinsi Jambi. *Jurnal Penelitian Hutan Dan Konservasi Alam*, 11(3), 299–313.
- [17] Pasandaran, E. (2006). Alternatif Kebijakan Pengendalian Konversi Lahan Sawah Beririgasi Di Indonesia. *Jurnal Litbang Pertanian*, 25(4), 123–129. Retrieved from <http://pustaka.litbang.pertanian.go.id/publikasip3254062.pdf>
- [18] Potter, L. (2008). Dayak Resistance To Oil Palm Plantations in West Kalimantan, Indonesia. In *Proceedings of the 17th Biennial Conference of the Asian Studies Association of Australia* (pp. 1–18).
- [19] Prabowo, S. A., Basuni, S., & Suharjito, D. (2010). Konflik Tanpa Henti: Permukiman dalam Kawasan Taman Nasional Halimun Salak (Enduring Conflict: Settlement in Halimun-Salak National Park Area). *Jurnal Manajemen Hutan Tropika*, XVI(3), 137–142.
- [20] Rokhdian, D. (2012). Alim Rajo Disembah, Piado Alim Rajo Disanggah: Ragam Bentuk Perlawanan Orang Rimba Makekal Hulu Terhadap Kebijakan Zonasi Taman Nasional Bukit Duabelas, Jambi. Universitas Indonesia.
- [21] Sardi, I. (2010). Konflik Sosial Dalam Pemanfaatan Sumberdaya Hutan (Study Kasus Di Taman Nasional Bukit Dua Belas Provinsi Jambi). Institut Pertanian Bogor.
- [22] Sembiring, E., Basuni, S., & Soekmadi, R. (2010). Resolusi Konflik Pengelolaan Taman Nasional Teluk Cenderawasih di Kabupaten Teluk Wondama. *Jurnal Manajemen Hutan Tropika*, XVI (2)(2), 84–91.
- [23] Senjaya, B. (2011). Resistensi Orang Rimba (Studi Tentang Perlawanan Orang Rimba Menghadapi Kebijakan Rencana Pengelolaan Taman Nasional Bukit Duabelas Propinsi Jambi). Universitas Gadjah Mada, Yogyakarta.
- [24] Soehartono, I. (2008). Metode Penelitian Sosial, Suatu Teknik Penelitian Bidang Kesejahteraan Sosial dan Ilmu Sosial Lainnya (vii). Bandung, Indonesia: Rosdakarya.
- [25] Steinebach, S., & Kunz, Y. (2017). Separating Sisters From Brothers : Ethnic Relations and Identity Politics in the Context of Indigenous Land Titling in Indonesia. *Austrian Journal of South-East Asian Studies*, 10(1), 47–64. <https://doi.org/10.14764/10.ASEAS-2017.1-4>
- [26] Suharko. (2016). Masyarakat Adat Versus Korporasi: Konflik Sosial Rencana Pembangunan Pabrik Semen di Kabupaten Pati Jawa Tengah Periode 2013-2016. *Jurnal Ilmu Sosial Dan Ilmu Politik*, 20(2), 97–116. <https://doi.org/10.22146/jsp.24776>
- [27] Sukmareni. (2012a, April). Alam Sumatera. KKI Warsi.
- [28] Sukmareni. (2012b, August). Alam Sumatera. KKI, 1–29.
- [29] Sylviani. (2008). Kajian Dampak Perubahan Fungsi Kawasan hutan Terhadap Masyarakat Sekitar (Study on The Impact of Changes in The Forest Function to The Community Around The Forest). *Penelitian Sosial Dan Ekonomi Kehutanan*, 5(3), 155–178.
- [30] Takiddin. (2014). Nilai - Nilai Kearifan Budaya Lokal Orang Rimba (Studi pada Suku Minoritas Rimba di Kecamatan Air Hitam Provinsi Jambi). *Jurnal Sosio Didaktika*, 1, No.2, 161–170.

- [31] Warsi, T. (2007). Alam Sumatera. KKI Warsi, 1–28.
- [32] Wiratno, K. (2012). Tipologi Konflik-Konflik Sosial di Kawasan Konservasi dan Upaya Solusinya. Retrieved from <http://konservasiwiratno.blogspot.co.id/2012/01/tipologi-konflik-konflik-sosial-di.html>
- [33] Yasmi, Y., Guernier, J., & Colfer, C. J. . (2009). Positive and negative aspects of forestry conflict: lessons from a decentralized forest management in Indonesia. *International Forestry Review*, 11(1), 98–110. <https://doi.org/10.1505/ifor.11.1.98>
- [34] Yasmi, Y., Kelley, L., & Enters, T. (2011). Forest Conflict in Asia and The Role of Collective Action in Its Management. *Communications*, (102), 30. <https://doi.org/10.2499/CAPRiWP102>.

